

**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND EMPLOYMENT PROBLEMS:
THE CASE OF AZERBAIJAN**

Nasirova Nargiz,

PHD Student, Lecturer

Sumgayit State University, Azerbaijan

Muradova Konul

Senior lecturer

Sumgayit State University, Azerbaijan

Abstract

This study examines the interrelation between social stratification and employment issues in the context of Azerbaijan. The article explores how education level, gender, and regional disparities affect employment opportunities and social mobility. Drawing on official data from the State Statistical Committee and the State Employment Agency, the research analyzes major trends in the labor market and identifies existing inequalities. The study highlights the impact of national employment strategies, including the “Employment Support Project” implemented with the support of the World Bank, on reducing social inequality and promoting self-employment. The results indicate that despite progress in employment policy, informal labor and limited social mobility remain key challenges. The paper concludes with recommendations to improve monitoring mechanisms, expand regional access to employment programs, and strengthen gender-inclusive labor market policies.

Keywords: social stratification, employment, inequality, social mobility, Azerbaijan, employment policy

The partition of society into social classes and the disparity between these classes according to resources, income, and opportunity are characteristics of social stratification. One social and economic factor that is crucial to the development of this stratification is employment. These days, one of the key markers of social justice, equality, and economic growth is the interplay between social structure and work interactions.

The aim of this study is to comparatively analyze the problems of social stratification and employment in the case of Azerbaijan, to determine the impact of social policy in the country and the advantages of different models. As we know, the models of Karl Marx, Max Weber and Davis-Moore occupy an important place among the theories of social stratification. Karl Marx proposed that economic classes are the main distinguishing factor, Max Weber presented social status and prestige as additional criteria, and Davis and Moore explained stratification as a functional necessity of society.[4] This study compares both economic and social indicators to determine how social inequality manifests itself in employment relations. The study is based on the comparative analysis method. Official indicators of the State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan, the State Employment Agency of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Azerbaijan were used as data sources.

The following indicators were taken into account when conducting the analysis:

- Total employment rate
- Unemployment rate
- Share of informal employment
- Income differences by educational level
- Share of women in the labor market

Discussion. According to preliminary data, as of March 1, 2025, the number of economically active population in Azerbaijan was 5,259.2 thousand people, of which 4,888.7 thousand were employed. Despite economic growth in recent years, informal employment and social inequality across regions remain. The relationship between education level and income is strong, but social mobility is limited. Youth make up 2.3 million people and 22.5 percent of the country's population. 52.9 percent of young people live in urban areas, and 47.1 percent in rural areas. It was additionally noted that last year, 54,535 young people aged 19-25 were registered as unemployed in Azerbaijan. This is 8,738 people less than in 2023. Thus, in 2024, 55,063 young people found work. This is 13,525 people more than in the previous year. Youth unemployment is around 10–12% and women's integration into the labor market is still low.[1] (table 1)

Tabel 1.

Indicator among young people	Azerbaijan
Unemployment rate	~5.5%
Female employment	39%
Informal work	High
Social mobility	Limited
Education and income relationship	Strong

Employment issues in Azerbaijan are compounded by regional disparities and low social mobility. The detrimental impacts of socioeconomic stratification are lessened in European nations by equal opportunity policies and state social policies.

The directions of employment policy in the Republic of Azerbaijan are determined by the document "Employment Strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2019–2030". The main goal of the strategy is to increase the competitiveness of the economy, as well as to ensure social justice and sustainable employment.

The document lists the following priority directions:

- Development of human capital and adaptation to labor market needs;
- Reduction of informal employment and legalization of labor relations;
- Creation of equal employment opportunities for youth, women and persons with disabilities;
- Integration of the digital economy and innovations into the labor market.

The implementation of this strategy is aimed at reducing social stratification, increasing social mobility, and eliminating interregional employment disparities.

The State Employment Agency [2], which is part of the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Azerbaijan, has a key institutional role in regulating the labor market, reducing unemployment, and implementing active employment measures in the country. The programs implemented within the framework of the Agency's activities are aimed at integrating social protection and employment policies. In particular, the "Employment Support Project", implemented with the support of the World Bank, is considered one of the key components of the country's employment strategy. [3] The project aims to expand the self-employment program based on best international practices, ensure access to small business opportunities for unemployed individuals, and create sustainable sources of income. Within the framework of this project, thousands of citizens were provided with training in business planning, financial literacy, and production-oriented activities, as well as equipment and initial capital support for citizens' individual farm and micro-business activities. As a result of the project, a culture of self-employment began to form in the country, which had a significant impact on reducing social stratification, especially increasing the economic activity of low-income groups. In this regard, the activities of the State Employment Agency act as an important institutional tool in ensuring social justice and equal opportunities and are carried out in full accordance with the Employment Strategy of Azerbaijan for 2019–2030.

Conclusion. Comparative analysis shows that there are direct links between social stratification and employment. Education, gender and regional differences further strengthen these links. If we look at European models, we see that the negative effects of

stratification are reduced through a system of social security and equal opportunities. In order to reduce the negative effects in Azerbaijan, it is possible to achieve the creation of equal employment opportunities across regions, to achieve the adaptation of education and vocational training systems to the labor market, to improve the development of legal mechanisms to reduce informal employment, and to strengthen social policies supporting the integration of women into the labor market. Employment policy directions in the Republic of Azerbaijan At the practical stage of implementation of the document "Employment Strategy of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2019–2030", some difficulties still remain: the persistence of informal jobs, wage inequality and youth employment problems.

Some of the micro businesses created within the framework of self-employment programs are unable to operate in the long term, and although they receive state support at the initial stage, they have difficulty adapting to market conditions and being competitive. Since the monitoring system of projects is not fully formed, changes in the economic situation, income level and social status of project participants are not systematically monitored. The fact that the areas where projects are actively implemented are mainly in cities such as Baku, Ganja, and Sumgayit limits the access of the population living in remote and rural areas of the country to employment programs. The poor awareness of the population about the programs is lower than the involvement of women and young people who have just graduated. Important recommendations for preventing these shortcomings are as follows:

1. Establishing a mechanism for systematic monitoring of self-employment and employment support projects and assessing their real results;
2. Achieving regional equality, that is, giving greater importance to the implementation of projects not only in large cities, but also in remote villages and regions;
3. Establishing and strengthening a support mechanism for women and youth, thereby ensuring their close participation in employment projects;
4. Using international experience, including the experience of successful projects implemented within the framework of the World Bank and the European Union.

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